

THE STUDY OF APHORISMS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS

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Annotation

Aphorisms in England and America have a lot in common. Aphorisms of England and America in the 20th century compared to German and French aphorisms. This article focuses on the aphoristic terminology adopted in these countries, noting that the terms "English aphorism" and "American aphorism" lack clear contours and that there is no solid theoretical work in this direction, except that currently in both countries it is noted that there are almost no separate books of aphorisms, and also that there are few scientific works on aphorisms, but the work on creating collections of aphorisms is well underway.

Keywords.

American literature, immoral paradox, humor, freedom of speech, aphoristic attributes, idiomatic, poetic.

Introduction.

English aphorism, on the one hand, strives for moral education (F. Bacon, J. Ruskin), and on the other hand, an immoral paradox (O. Wilde, B. Shaw). In the form of a paradox, the aesthetic structure of the aphorism (combination of contrasting concepts) is fully revealed, and at the same time its aesthetic content is disintegrated, because the aphorism is no longer based on the assumption of eternal, monumental laws. Being and thinking, but in their unexpected, effective removal and rejection, moreover, the edges of good and evil, truth and falsehood are lost in the game of opposites. Famous writers and thinkers such as Bernard Shaw, Gilbert Keith Chesterton, and Oscar Wilde, who created English aphorisms throughout the 19th and 20th centuries, made a great contribution. Their aphorisms are distinguished by paradox and unusual form. Bernard Shaw is the author of introductory aphorisms, which are distinguished mainly by their paradoxical form.

It is not for nothing that F. Engels, who appreciated Shaw's talent, called him a "paradoxical novelist". Shaw's aphorisms are unusual, incompatible with the foundations of bourgeois society, and are characterized by their sharp criticism. Shaw himself said: "...paradoxes are the only truth" and "fortunately there is an

outlet for the truth: what is forbidden to be said seriously can be said with humor"⁶⁰.

Literature review. The great master of aphorism was Gilbert Keith Chesterton, who weaved aphorisms into his original essays with ease and skill. Like Shaw, he often presented aphorisms in a paradoxical fashion, using them to draw readers' attention to old but timeless truths. It should be said that during the time when these writers were working in England, after the elegant and beautiful paradoxes appeared by O. Wilde, the passion for paradox was especially strong. The aphorists of the time even had to show a certain courage in defending "general truths" as their opponents called aphorisms.⁶¹ Chesterton's aphorisms reflect his negative attitude towards the customs and laws of bourgeois society, but at the same time they are mostly optimistic. He writes, "I knew the world was dead, but I always thought it would end at least with a trumpet call, but by no means with weeping. And indeed a kind of phantasmagoria appears: the old people dance incessantly and laugh contagiously, and the young people are sad and sad "; "... life now, as always, is a priceless blessing; you can prove it by putting a pistol to a pessimist's head"; "... most modern philosophers ... are ready to sacrifice happiness for the sake of progress, the meaning of any progress lies only in happiness"⁶². B. Shaw and G. Chesterton's inclination towards the paradoxical form of aphorism can be seen as a traditional feature of English aphorism. Aphorisms of this form were written by U. Shenston, D. Swift, D.S. Halifax, F. Chesterfield; some of the mentioned authors also published separate books of aphorisms. Currently, such books are hardly published in England, but introductory aphorisms can be found in the works of many writers: D. Galsworthy, G. Wells, S. Maugham, and others. Aphorisms of English philosophers B. Russell and A. Whitehead. is also famous all over the world.⁶³ (Fedorenko, Sokolskaya 1990: 159). As for American literature, it can be seen that it is not as rich in aphorisms as in English. Mark Twain's aphoristic work is very noteworthy. His "Notebooks", first published only in 1935, are full of aphorisms, in which humor is often combined with the sharpest satire. For example, one can cite his characteristic aphorism: "We have received three precious

⁶⁰ Дмитриева О.А. Культурно-языковые характеристики пословиц и афоризмов: (на материале фр. и рус. яз.): автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук [Текст] / Дмитриева О.А.; Волгогр. гос. пед. ун-т. – Волгоград, 1997. – Б. 134.

⁶¹ Федоренко Н.Т., Соколская Л.И. Афористика [Текст] / Н.Т. Федоренко, Л.И. Соколская. – М.: Наука, 1990. – Б. 158.

⁶² Королкова А.В. Русская афористика в контексте фразеологии: дис. ... д-ра филол. наук [Текст] / Королкова А.В. – Смоленск, 2005. – Б. 132.

⁶³ Федоренко Н.Т., Соколская Л.И. Афористика [Текст] / Н.Т. Федоренко, Л.И. Соколская. – М.: Наука, 1990. – Б. 159.

gifts in America: freedom of speech, freedom of conscience, and prudence, which prevents us from using them.”⁶⁴ His words sound like a slogan for all the progressive forces of the motherland: "Peace, happiness, brotherhood of nations - we need it in this world. M. Twain appreciated the aphorism and rightly noted: "The right dose of the aphorism: minimum words, maximum meaning." Twain's aphorisms are perfectly suited to this dose, and besides, they are very original, witty and optimistic. There are aphorisms in the works of E. Hemingway and some other authors. The aphorisms of American philosophers George Santayana and John Dewey are known to many. As we mentioned earlier, no solid theoretical works were created in the aphoristic direction in America and England. However, in England and America, the aphorism certainly exists, but one gets the impression that there are almost no books of separate aphorisms there, and the predominance of the introductory aphorism, which is not recognized abroad. A relatively small development of the Anglo-American aphorism.⁶⁵ The creation of reference literature on aphorisms is well underway in these countries. The most complete collections and encyclopedias of aphorisms of world writers and famous figures are published in English; they are carefully compiled and systematically published.⁶⁶ For example, consider the three most famous encyclopedias compiled by B. Stevenson, D. Bartlett and Oxford University. Stevenson's encyclopedia is compiled on a subjective basis and mainly contains aphorisms of world writers. The aphorisms in it are selected for the names of a large number of objects, and it contains 2,817 pages. Each citation contains a reference to the source: author, work title, year of publication, volume, chapter, and often pages. The book contains aphorisms of ancient and modern authors.

Research Methodology.

At the same time, today in linguistics there is no generally accepted concept that should be called an aphorism. In general linguistic reference literature, the term aphorism is either vaguely interpreted or not. Therefore, it is not included in four versions of the fundamental encyclopedia "Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary" (1990, 2002, "Linguistics" - 1998, 2000) and is not included in most dictionaries of linguistic terms, for example, O.S. Akhmanova (1966, 1969/2004), T.V. Foal (2005, 6th edition - 2016), V.D. Starichonka (2008) and others in

⁶⁴ Душенко К.В. Мысли, афоризмы и шутки знаменитых мужчин [Текст] / К.В. Душенко. – М.: Эксмо, 2003. – Б. 239.

⁶⁵ Королкова А.В. Русская афористика в контексте фразеологии: дис. ... д-ра филол. наук [Текст] / Королкова А.В. – Смоленск, 2005. – Б. 141.

⁶⁶ Шумакова А.П. Французский афоризм как текст: дис. ... канд. филол. наук [Текст] / Шумакова А.П. – Смоленск, 2006. – Б. 164.

“Dictionary of Linguistic Terms” O.S. Akhmanova noted only aphoristic attributes. For example, consider the three most famous encyclopedias compiled by B. Stevenson, D. Bartlett and Oxford University. Stevenson’s encyclopedia is compiled on a subjective basis and mainly contains aphorisms of world writers. The aphorisms in it are selected for the names of a large number of objects, and it contains 2,817 pages. Each citation contains a reference to the source: author, work title, year of publication, volume, chapter, and often pages. The book contains aphorisms of ancient and modern authors.

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Analysis and results.

Thus, in linguistics, the definition of an aphorism is "short (or concise)", "original", "deep", "marked (in form)", "expressive", "pleasant", "paradoxical", "product" concepts are used. "authorship" is widely used, "memorable", "unique", etc., are not actually linguistic (they do not belong to the metalanguage of linguistics). Recently, the search for a single defining feature has become noticeable, on the basis of which all sentences of different content and different syntactic form, usually called aphorisms, can be combined into one group (type) of language units. As such a sign, "conceptualization" is proposed (reflecting the most relevant

⁶⁷ Ахманова О.С. Словар лингвистических терминов. М.: Сов. энциклопедия, 1966. – Б. 60.

⁶⁸ Русский язык: энциклопедия / гл. ред. Ю.Н. Караулов. М.: Большая российская энциклопедия, 2008. – Б. 60.

concepts of "concepts" for native speakers)⁶⁹, "passporting" (knowledge of the author's language by native speakers)⁷⁰ "reproduction" (retention in the minds of native speakers and repetition in a "finished" form in speech)⁷¹, as well as "idiomatic" (expression of content that goes beyond the sum of the meanings of lexical components), "poetic" (expressiveness of verbal form), etc. However, these and similar features are not unique. in aphorisms, but also in other types of superstructure (phraseological units, catchphrases, literary quotations, etc.) does not narrow the concept of aphorism to a specific type of linguistic unit, but expands it to any statement (freely). or stable), conceptualized or passported or repeated, or idiomatic or poetic (expressive), etc.

In the first case, a certain number of non-unique objects are reported, for example:

All days of the week are good; It will be all the same a hundred years hence (proverbs);

(All days of the week are good; Even after a hundred years (proverbs);)

Or even about single objects that make up a single set of elements, for example:

The devil can cite Scripture for his purpose (W. Shakespeare);

(The devil may quote scripture for his purpose (W. Shakespeare);)

With the universal (universal) generalization, texts report not about a set of objects, their properties or relationships, but about entire classes. In this case, the subject of the message can be only non-single objects, the number of which is not limited by anything and cannot be clearly known (determined) with a neutral perception of the statement (outside the context of the speech). any cases (which are cognitively insignificant for native speakers), even if their quantitative size is deliberately differentiated by the author of the aphorism for one or another purpose (artistic, rhetorical, etc.). For example:

Some Like It Hot (movie title); Where ignorance is bliss, tis folly to be wise (T. Gray);

Some Like It Hot (film title);

Where ignorance is bliss, wisdom is folly (T. Gray);

The official criterion for classifying this generalized phrase as an aphorism is, firstly, its application to the whole class of subjects (objects, actions) it informs in

⁶⁹ Королкова А.В. Русская афористика. М.: Флинта: Наука, 2005. – Б. 27.

⁷⁰ Королкова А.В. Русская афористика. М.: Флинта: Наука, 2005. – Б. 29-30.

⁷¹ Мечковская Н.Б. Жанры афористики и градация высказываний по степени идиоматичности // Жанры речи. Вып. 6. 2009. – Б. 81.

speech, and secondly, its impossibility to use it by itself. about a limited set or identity of entities (objects, actions) without any inconsistency with native speakers' practical or theoretical experience (i.e., between the meaning of the statement and the presupposition an unresolvable cognitive contradiction) discourse to inform. For example:

Poor bird! (not used in relation to the whole class of pitiful birds, it is reflected in the context of the author, the protagonist of the film feels sorry for the bird that he heard only in his dream, he only feels sorry for the bird that decided to fly. He looked at the sun and burned his wings; this winged phrase in the speech "to die from what happened" is evidenced by its semantically non-discrete use as a phrase to indicate playful pity (yet deliberately enhanced by weeping).

Art is long, life is short.

Generalization of reality in the semantics of aphorisms can be accompanied by figurative motivation of both the meanings of their separate lexical components and their general meaning. At the same time, individual revised lexical components of an aphorism may not have a generalized content in the direct sense, they may denote unique, including unique objects.

Conclusion/Recommendations. In this regard, the most urgent and important problem in the study of an aphorism as an object of linguistics is, first of all, to determine its specific linguistic features (features), on the basis of which it will be possible to consistently distinguish aphorisms. The purpose of writing the article is to identify and describe the minimum number of the most linguistically significant signs (features) of the aphorism as a linguistic object, as well as to determine their mandatory / optional nature, specificity / generality (for the aphorism).

Such differentiation of generalization at the sentence level is of fundamental importance in describing the semantics of an aphorism and defining its concept as a linguistic object, and therefore requires a separate explanation.

All content-generalized sentences are divided into those whose generalization has a factual (registration) character and those that have a universal (general) character. In a real (registering) generalization, a word is about objects (subjects, properties, processes, events) and their specific set (if their number is known to the participants of the speech act) or reports in the form of registration sets (if there are any of them). They are not clearly known to the participants of the speech act, but they are considered limited, that is, they can be clearly defined if desired).

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